

humAlne

Hybrid Human-AI Decision Support for Enhanced Human Empowerment in Dynamic Situations

What is HumAlne?

HumAlne is a joint effort of 17 partners to create a revolutionary Operating System platform for enhancing the collaboration between Humans and AI across various industrial sectors. This platform integrates advanced AI learning paradigms, such as Active Learning, Neuro Symbolic Learning, Swarm Learning, and eXplainable AI, in dynamic, unstructured environments across 5 sectors, acting as project pilots.

Project Facts

- Total Budget:** € 7,658,375
- Project duration:** 36 months
- Start Date:** 1st October 2023
- Project Coordinator:** GFT ITALIA SRL
- Call identifier:** HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-02

Making the best out of Humans & Artificial Intelligence Systems Collaboration

Our 5 Pilots

Smart Manufacturing

Smart Cities

Smart Healthcare

Smart Finance

Smart Energy

Contact us:

Interested in joining our community?

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www.humaine-horizon.eu

- info@humaine-horizon.eu
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